

Phonological domains in Standard Spanish

? lexical form = content word, non-lexical form = function word ?

I Language Profile

#speakers: 28 million (Spain); 322 million (Spain & world)

contact languages: English, French, Nahuatl (in LA)

status: official language

prospects: maintenance

structural results: light lexical and light structural borrowing

borrowed forms: special treatment?

V phonemes: a e i o u

C phonemes: (some orthographic symbols in brackets)

	Labial	Dental	Alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Uvular
Plosive	p b		t d		k g	
Affricate			tʃ (ch)			
Fricative	f	θ (z)	s			χ (j)
Nasal	m		n	ɲ (ñ)		
Liquid:Vibrant			r r: (rr)			
Liquid:Lateral			l	ʎ (ll)		

II Morpheme Types

inflectional: suffix, particle (see VII)

derivational: prefix, suffix (see VII)

III Syllable

a) **types:** minimal V, maximal CCVC, i.e. V, CV, VC, CCV, CVC, CCVC or (C(C))V(C)

NB: C.CC but *CC.C (CC.C only in foreign words, reduced to C.C)

trans.por.te [traⁿs] 'transport', *abs.truso* [a^βs'truso] 'abstruse')

b) if **VV**, then diphthong (at least one of them must be *i* or *u*, see table below)

c) **minimal free form:** V function words minimally V (*a* 'to'; *y* [i], *e* [e] 'and'; *o* [ɔ], *u* [u] 'or')

content words minimally CV, VC (*tú* '2s', *él* '3s.M')

d) **V-initial word?** YES lexical forms: *antes* 'before', *ola* 'wave'

non-lexical : *un* 'DET.3sM.indef

NB: ?-insertion / #_V (other V-initial syllables undergo resyll if possible)

e) **V-only word?** YES (lexical forms: -- non-lexical: *y* [i] 'and', *o* [ɔ] 'or')

f) **di-/polysyllabic & monomorphemic:** *ca.sa* 'house', *en.fer.mo* 'ill'

g) **Phonotactics:**

	initial ONSET	ONSET	NUCLEUS	CODA	final CODA
simple	*/r/ (but /R/ okay)	any C	any V	any C	*{pb t kg f m}
					*tʃ, ñ
complex	{pb td kg f} + {l r}		V _y , _y V, _y v _y V _y V={a e o} v={u i}		C + s (=Cs)
	*tʃ				

h) **Variations across lexical categories?** Affixes with complex onset are non-inflectional and are loaned: -cracia, -crata, proto-, pluto-, etc.

i) **Super-heavy syllables (CV:C,CVCC)?** only C + VV(V) + C (*pues* 'so', *cam.bi-áis* 'change-2p.PRES', *con.ti.nu-áis* 'continue-2p.PRES'). **Is that considered superheavy?**

j) **Diphthongs:** in any syllable? YES (*mues.tra*, *.d-io*. 'give-3s.PT', *vi.v-íó* 'live-3s.PT')

Diphthongs in affix/clitic? - In affixes. (-*ais* '2p.AGR', -*zuelo* 'DIM', *idio-* 'own', *leuco-* 'white')

IV Tone and stress

Spanish is non-tonal and has distinctive stress.

a) **patterns and domains:** free accent on last 3 syllables

b) **combinatory restrictions and domains:** domain for stress is stem+suffix(es); stressed stem: '*ca.sa* 'house'

stressed suffix: *co.'m-íó* 'eat.3s.PT.PFV'

co.'m-i.a 'eat.3s.PT.IPFV'

c) **secondary stress:** NO

d) **domains for word stress:** stem+suffix(es)

domains for phrase/clause/sentence/utterance stress: --

e) **specialized instances of stress and domains:** --

f) **patterns of intonation and domains:** --

V Other non-concat. processes

P-rules between morpheme1 & morpheme2 (part 1) (orthographic representations in italics)

process	within stem	within affix	within syll.
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d: Fricativization ¹ of /y,w/ /#(pf)_V or V_V	/aya/ > ['a.ɣa] 'private tutoress'	--	--
e ² : Lengthening of /r/ /{n,l,s} . _ and /#_	<i>al.re.de.dor</i> 'around'	<i>re-hacer</i> 'to redo'	n/a
f: Place-assimilation of lateral & nasals /_ obstr	<i>cuándo</i> 'when' <i>campo</i> 'field'	<i>estadounid-ense</i> 'US-' (adj) <i>habl-ando</i> 'speak-PROG'	ruled out by phonotactic constraints
h: Fricativization of /b d g/ (not after # or homorganic [-cont] sonorants)	<i>lado</i> ['la.ðo] 'side' (but: <i>caldo</i> [kaldɔ] 'broth', <i>bien</i> [byen] 'well')	<i>odontólogo</i> [ɔ.ðon.'to.lo.ɣo] 'dentist'	ruled out by phonotactic constraints
m: Voicing-assimilation of s /_ C[+voice]	<i>desde</i> ['dez.ðe] 'since'	sequence does not occur within affixes	ruled out by phonotactic constraints

P-rules between morpheme1 & morpheme2 (part 2)

process	initial	prefix-stem	stem-stem	stem-suffix	suffix-suffix
d: Fricativization ³ of /y,w/ /#(pf)_V or V_V	[weɰɔ] > [ɣeɰɔ] (> [weɰɔ]) 'egg'	/sub-yugar/ >[sub.ɣu.'ɣar] 'to subjugate'	??	--	--
e ⁴ : Lengthening of /r/ /{n,l,s} . _ and /#_	<i>rollo</i> [r:ɔ.ʎo] 'roll'	<i>en.-roll-ar</i> 'to roll up'	<i>mata-rratas</i> 'rat poison' <i>pele-rrajo</i> 'redhaired'	sequence does not occur	sequence does not occur

¹ This process does not apply in fast speech, where the affected segments are pronounced as semi-vowels.

² /r/ [r],[r:] and /R/ [r:] only contrast intervocalically. Complementary distributed over (in?) other environments: /R/ only occurs word-initially (incl. 2nd part of a compound, e.g. subRayar, alRededor), /r/ elsewhere.

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f: Place-assimilation of lateral & nasals /_ obstr	ruled out by phonotactic constraints	<i>melan-colía</i> [me.laŋ.ko.'li.a] 'melancholy'	<i>bien-venido</i> [byem.be'ni.do] 'welcome' /cien pie-s/ > <i>ciempiés</i> 'centipede'	<i>bon-dad</i> 'kindness'	sequence does not occur
h: Fricativization of /b d g/ (not after # or homorganic [-cont] sonorants)		<i>bien</i> [byen] 'well' <i>des-bordar</i> [dez.βɔr.ðar] 'to exceed'	<i>autobús</i> [β] 'bus'	<i>desbord-ar</i> [dez.βɔr.ðar] 'to exceed'	<i>habl-a-do</i> [ʔa.'βla. 'speak.PTCP.PT'
m: Voicing-assimilation of s /_ C[+voice]	sequence does not occur (*#sC, *.sC)	<i>des-bordar</i> [dez.βɔr.ðar] 'to exceed'	??	sequence does not occur	sequence does not occur

P-rules with domain = stem

process	stem-initial	within stem	stem-final
Epenthesis of e /#(prefix)_ sC	/ (in-)stabl-el > (in)establ-e '(un)stable'	--	n/a
Diphthongization of underlying vowels in certain stems when stressed	/o.vo/ > <i>huevo</i> ['we.vɔ] 'egg'	[kon't-ar] 'tell-INF' > ['kwen.t-o] 'tell-1s.PRES'	--

VI "Free" grammatical morphemes

- their phonol. interactions with other morphemes: phonologically weak, attaching to following element
- their syllable structure and phonotactics: (C)V
- their tone/stress: *no* 'NEG' can be stressed contrastively

(AUTOTYP-entries for Spanish)

form	morphotype	gloss	host/dom restr.	fusion	ex.
'a'	POSwd (~preposition)	DOM/DAT	restricted to <i>NP</i> ⁵	concat.	<i>Ve-o a ella</i> . "I see her"
'de'	POSwd (~preposition)	POSS/GEN	restricted to <i>NP</i> ⁶	concat.	<i>el libro de ella</i> "her book"
'no'	Formative	NEG	restricted to (<i>pn</i>) <i>VP</i>	concat.	<i>No te ve-o</i> . "I don't see you."

VII Polymorphemic forms

patterns

prefix (nonverbal)	prefix (verbal)	suffix (non-verbal)	suffix (verbal)	infix/circumfix/clitics
see below	de(s)-, re-, en-	see below	see below	% (but see notes below)

a note on Spanish "clitics": The object pronouns are often described as clitics. The following table gives an overview. I wasn't sure where to put the present-participle-constructions, so I highlighted them grey.

		Old Spanish	Modern Spanish
finite forms	declarative, interrogative (today only preverbal)	preverbal : me dijo 'told me' lo fueron diciendo 'were saying it' ⁷	

⁵ i.e. followed by DET, pronoun or proper noun

⁶ s.o.

⁷ preverbal object-pronouns in progressive constructions (i.e. using the present participle) are named "clitic climbing"

		postverbal: díjome 'told me' estában me diciendo 'were telling me'	* díjome
	imperative (NEG preverbal, AFF postverbal)	preverbal: No me lo digas! 'Don't tell me!' postverbal: Dígame! 'Tell me!'	
non-finite forms	present participle	postverbal: diciéndome 'telling me'	

a note on Spanish "infixes": F. Rainer (1993) adopts the analysis of Martínez-Celdrán (1978) in that the diminutive is an infix in certain adverbs and certain proper nouns.

cerca 'near' > *cerqu-it-a* 'very near', *lejos* 'far' > *lej-it-os* 'very far', *ahora* 'now' > *ahor-it-a* 'right now', *ahora misma* 'right now' > *ahora mism-it-o* 'right now';

Carlos 'Charles' > *Carl-it-os* 'Charly'

However, in *casa* 'house' > *cas-it-a* 'little house' it is considered a suffix (DIM.FEM.SG).

verbal suffixes : verbal inflection is suffixal (V = theme vowel: a - e - i), maximum 4 syllables

PRES	V-AGR	Indefinido		Imperfecto	V-(b)a ⁸ -AGR	FUT V-r-AGR		Cond.	V-r-i-a-AGR
-o	-V-mos	-V	-V-mos	-V-(b)a	-V-(b)a-mos	-V-r-e	-V-r-emos	V-r-i-a	V-r-i-a-mos
-V-s	-V-is	-V-ste	-V-steis	-V-(b)a-s	-V-(b)a-is	-V-r-as	-V-r-eis	V-r-i-a-s	V-r-i-a-is
-V	-V-n	-o/io	-V-ro-n	-V-(b)a	-V-(b)a-n	-V-r-a	-V-r-an	V-r-i-a	V-r-i-a-n

PTCP.IPFV: -a-ndo, -ie-ndo

⁸ evidence for viv-í-(b)a "s/he/I lived" comes from ir > i-**ba**(s); í-**ba**-mos, i-**ba**-is, i-**ba**-n
analog: subj.IPFV

PTCP.PFV: -a-do, -i-do

non-verbal suffixes

nominal plural-suffix	-(e)s	árbol-es 'tree-PL', casa-s 'house-PL'
plural-agreement suffix (on Adj, Det)	-(o)s, -(a)s	árboles (<i>m</i>) / casas (<i>f</i>) grande-s 'big trees/houses' árboles viej-os 'old trees' vs. casas viej-as 'old houses' much-os árboles 'many trees' vs. much-as casas 'many houses'
adverbial suffix	-mente	fácil (Adj) > fácilmente (Adv), completo > completamente
augmentative (nouns, adj.)	-ote/-ota, -ón/-ona, -azo/-aza	árbol > arbolote, hombre > hombrón, perro > perrazo grande > grandote
augmentative (adjectives)	-ísimo/-ísima	rico > riquísimo
diminutive (nouns, adj, adv)	-(c)ito/-(c)ita, -illo/-illa, -uelo/-zuela,	perro 'dog' > perrito 'little dog', perros 'dogs' > perritos 'little dogs'
pejorative (nouns)	-aco/-aca, -acho/-acha, -ajo/-aja, -ote/-ota, -ucho/-ucha	casa > casucha, rico > ricacho

more nominal suffixes

Suffix	English correspondent	Examples
-aje	-age	<i>kilometraje</i> , mileage
-ancia	-ancy	<i>discrepancia</i> , discrepancy
-arquía	-archy	<i>monarquía</i> , monarchy
-ático	-atic	<i>lunático</i> , lunatic
-V-ble	-ble	<i>manejable</i> , manageable
-cida, -cidio	-cide	<i>insectida</i> , insecticide
-cion	-tion	<i>agravacion</i> , aggravation
-cracia	-cracy	<i>democracia</i> , democracy
-crata	-crat	<i>burócrata</i> , bureaucrat
-dad	-ity	<i>pomposidad</i> , pomposity

-esa, -iz, -isa	-ess	actriz , actress
-fico, -fica	-fic	horrífico , horrific
-filo, filia	-phile	bibliofilo , bibliophile
-fobia	-phobia	claustrofobia , claustrophobia
-fono	-phone	teléfono , telephone
-icio, -icia	-ice	avaricia , avarice
-ificar	-ify	dignificar , to dignify
-ismo	-ism	budismo , Buddhism
-ista	-ist	dentista , dentist
-itís	-itis	flebitis , phlebitis
-tude	-tude	latitud , latitude
-izo	-ish	rojizo , reddish
-or, -ora	-er	pintor , painter
-osa, -oso	-ous	maravilloso , marvelous
Suffix	Meaning	Examples
-ada	similar to English suffix "-ful" or "-load"	cucharada , spoonful
-ado, -ido	can indicate similarity to root word	dolorido , painful
-al	indicates a tree or grove	manzanal , apple tree
-anza	makes noun forms of some verbs	enseñanza , education
-ario	indicates profession or place	bibliotecario , librarian
-azo	a blow of the object of the root word	estacazo , a hit with a stick
-dero	indicates instrument, means, or capacity	lavadero , laundry
-dor	indicates agent or place; sometimes similar to "-er"	jugador , player; comedor , diner
-dura	indicates the effect of an action	picadura , puncture
-ear	common verb ending, often used with coined words	emaillear , to email
-ense	indicates place of origin	estadounidense , of the United States
-ería	place where items are made or sold	zapatería , shoe store
-ero, -era	variety of meanings relating to root word	sombrero , hat; vaquero , cowboy
-és	indicates place of origin	holandés , Dutch
-eza	makes abstract nouns from adjectives	pureza , purity

Loaned prefixes (Latin, Greek)

holo-	todo <i>whole</i>	holocausto
homea-, hom(o)-	parecido <i>alike; same</i>	homeopatía, homólogo
horo-	hora <i>hour</i>	horóscopo
icono-	imagen <i>image</i>	iconoclasta

icter-	amarillez <i>yellow</i>	ictericia
ide(o)-	idea <i>idea</i>	ideograma, ideología
idio-	propio <i>own</i>	idiosincracia; idioma
iso-	igual <i>same</i>	isomorfo; isoterma
kilo-	mil <i>thousand</i>	kilogramo
leuco-	blanco <i>white</i>	leucocito
lexic(o)-	lenguaje <i>language</i>	lexicología
lit(o)-	pedra <i>stone</i>	litografía; litiasis
log(o)-	palabra, ciencia <i>word</i>	lógica; logogrifo
macro-	grande <i>big</i>	macrocosmos; macrocéfalo
mega(lo)-	grande <i>huge</i>	megalomanía; megáfono
melan(o)-	negro <i>black</i>	melancolía, melanosis
mel(o)-	canto, música <i>music</i>	melodía
meso-	medio <i>middle</i>	mesopotámico
meteor(o)-	elevado, en el aire <i>high</i>	meteoro; meteorito
metr(o)-	medida <i>measure</i>	metrónomo; métrica
micr(o)-	pequeño <i>small</i>	microcosmos; microbio; micra
miel(o)-	médula <i>marrow</i>	mielitis
mio-	músculo <i>muscle</i>	miocardio
miri(s)-	diez mil <i>ten thousand</i>	miriópodo; miriámetro
mis(o)-	odiar <i>hate</i>	misántropo; misógino

mit(o) -	fábula, leyenda <i>fable, legend</i>	mitología, mítico
mnemo-	memoria <i>memory</i>	mnemotecnia
mon(o)-	único <i>unique</i>	monarquía; monolito
morfo-	forma <i>form</i>	morfología
nau-	nave <i>ship</i>	náutico, náusea
necro-	muerto <i>death</i>	necrología, necrópolis
nefr(o)-	riñón <i>kidney</i>	nefritis
neo-	nuevo <i>new</i>	neologísimo; neófito
neumo-	pulmón <i>lung</i>	neumotórax; neumonía
neur(o)-	nervio <i>nerve</i>	neurosis; neuralgia
noso-	enfermedad <i>illness</i>	nosomíntica
octa-, octo-	ocho <i>eight</i>	octaedro; octágono
odont(o)-	diente <i>teeth</i>	odontólogo
oftalm(o)-	ojo <i>eye</i>	oftalmía
olig(o)-	poco <i>little</i>	oligarquía
onir(o)-	sueño <i>dream</i>	oniromancia
onoma-	nombre <i>name</i>	onomástica
onto-	ser <i>to be</i>	ontología
ornito-	pájaro <i>bird</i>	ornitología
oro-	montaña <i>mountain</i>	orografía
orto-	recto <i>straight</i>	ortografía, ortopedia

oste(o)-	hueso <i>bone</i>	osteoblasto, otitis
ot(o)-	oído <i>ear</i>	otólogo, otitis
oxi-	ácido <i>acid</i>	oxígeno
paleo-	antiguo <i>old</i>	paleolítico, paleografía
pan-, pant(o)-	todo <i>all</i>	panacea, panteísmo, pantógrafo
paqui -	espeso <i>thick</i>	paquidermo
pato-	enfermedad <i>illness</i>	patología
ped-	niño <i>child</i>	pedagogía, pediatría
penta-	cinco <i>five</i>	pentágono
pir(o)-	fuego <i>fire</i>	pirotecnia, piritita
pitec	mono <i>monkey</i>	pitecantropo, piteco
plast-	formar <i>to form; shape</i>	plasticidad
pleur-	costado <i>side</i>	pleura, pleuritis
pluto-	rico <i>rich</i>	plutocracia
pod(o) -	pie <i>feet</i>	podómetro, podio
poli-	muchos <i>many</i>	polígrafo, poliedro
proto-	primero <i>first</i>	prototipo
psic(o)-, sic(o)-, psiqui-	alma <i>soul</i>	psiquiatría, psicología
ptero-	ala <i>wing</i>	pterodáctilo
quiro-, cir-	mano <i>hand</i>	quiromancia, cirugía
rino-	naríz <i>nose</i>	rinoceronte

rizo-	raíz <i>root</i>	rizófago, rizoma
sacar(o) -	azúcar <i>sugar</i>	sacarina, sacarosa
sarco-	carne <i>beef</i>	sarcoma, sarcófago
sema-	señal, significación <i>signal</i>	semáforom, semántica
seudo-	falso <i>false</i>	seudónimo
sider(o)-	hierro <i>iron</i>	siderurgia, siderosis
somat(o)-	cuerpo <i>body</i>	somático, somatología
taqui-	rápido <i>fast</i>	taquigrafía, taquicardia
tauro-	toro <i>bull</i>	tauromaquia
tauto-	lo mismo <i>identical</i>	tautología
taxi-	taza <i>cup</i>	taxímetro
tecn(o) -	arte <i>art</i>	tecnología, técnica
tele-	lejos <i>far</i>	teléfono, televisión
teo-	Dios <i>God</i>	teología, teocracia
terapeut-	que cura <i>to heal</i>	terapéutica
term(o) -	calor <i>heat</i>	termómetro, térmico
tetra-	cuatro <i>four</i>	tetraedro
toco-	parto <i>obstetric</i>	tocología
top(o)-	lugar <i>place</i>	tópico
toxico-	veneno <i>poison</i>	toxicología
urano-	cielo <i>sky</i>	uranometría

xeno-	extranjero <i>stranger</i>	xenofobia
xero-	seco <i>dry</i>	xeroftalmía
xilo-	madera <i>wood</i>	xilófago, xilografía
zoo-	animal <i>animal</i>	zoología